

Pharmacological Safety of Lithium Ascorbate

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Abstract

Lithium ascorbate is an organic lithium salt proposed as a potentially lower-toxicity alternative to conventional lithium compounds. The present study aimed to evaluate its preclinical safety profile through an integrated assessment of repeated-dose toxicity, allergenic potential, pharmacological safety, and selected toxicological endpoints in animal models. Three GLP-compliant studies were conducted using rats, mice, and guinea pigs. Repeated-dose toxicity was assessed in male and female rats following daily intragastric administration of lithium ascorbate at doses of 10, 100, and 500 mg/kg for 180 days. Additional evaluations included local irritant action, immunotoxicity, mutagenicity-related endpoints, reproductive-organ morphology, and allergenicity testing. Pharmacological safety was examined in male Wistar rats after a single intragastric administration at doses of 10, 50, and 150 mg/kg, with assessment of respiratory, cardiovascular, and central nervous system function.

Lithium ascorbate did not produce detectable adverse effects on respiratory rate, electrocardiographic parameters, blood pressure, body temperature, behavior, or exploratory activity following single-dose administration. No sensitizing, immunotoxic, mutagenic, local irritant, or reproductive-organ effects were observed in the applied experimental models. Repeated administration at 10 mg/kg was not associated with overt clinical toxicity. However, higher doses were associated with reduced tolerability, including polyuria, polydipsia, altered body-weight dynamics, and mortality in female rats. These findings support continued investigation of lithium ascorbate while highlighting the need for additional toxicokinetic and long-term safety studies.

Keywords: lithium ascorbate; psychiatry; animal studies; pharmacology

Introduction

Lithium salts have long-standing pharmacological relevance, particularly in psychiatry, where lithium compounds are used for the treatment of mood disorders (Kessing, 2024). However, the clinical use of conventional lithium preparations is limited by concerns related to tolerability, dose-dependent toxicity, and the need for careful safety monitoring (Baumgartner et al., 1997; McKnight et al., 2012; Gitlin, 2016; Rybakowski, 2018; Fiorillo et al., 2023; Kessing, 2024). These limitations have contributed to continued interest in alternative lithium salts that may provide pharmacological activity at lower doses or with improved safety characteristics (Torshin et al., 2022; Rastashanskiy, 2020; Rastashanskiy & Ostrenko, 2020).

Lithium Ascorbate

One of the latest developments in terms of lithium salts on the pharmacological market is lithium ascorbate by Normopharm (Torshin et al., 2022). Lithium ascorbate is an organic salt of lithium and ascorbic acid (Vitamin C).

Lithium ascorbate is a lower-toxicity lithium salt with reported potential anxiolytic, antidepressant, neuroprotective, and memory-supporting effects (Torshin et al., 2022; Rastashanskiy, 2020; Rastashanskiy & Ostrenko, 2020).

Although lithium ascorbate has been proposed as a potentially lower-toxicity organic lithium salt with neuropsychiatric relevance, its use as a pharmacologically active compound requires systematic preclinical safety characterization, including repeated-dose toxicity, genotoxicity-related endpoints, reproductive and immunotoxicity, allergenic potential, and effects on major physiological systems.

The tested drug developer and the organization responsible for arranging the preclinical studies is Normopharm LLC. The studies were performed in accordance with GLP OECD principles (OECD, 1998a).

The test substance was Lithium Ascorbate, substance code T-1.28/21, supplied by Normopharm LLC, Russia. The substance was manufactured according to Good Manufacturing Practice. The control substance was listed as vehicle code M-1.28/21; saline solution, Grotex LLC, Russia.

Study 1: Toxic properties, local irritant action, elements of mutagenic action, elements of reproductive and immunotoxicity

Materials and methods

Study design and regulatory framework

An experimental preclinical safety study was conducted to evaluate the toxic properties, local irritant potential, elements of mutagenic action, reproductive toxicity, and immunotoxicity of lithium ascorbate following repeated administration in rats. The study was performed at the Laboratory of Drug Toxicology, Federal State Budgetary Institution “Golikov Scientific and Clinical Center for Toxicology of the Federal Medical and Biological Agency,” Saint Petersburg, Russia. The study was conducted in accordance with Good Laboratory Practice principles.

Test system and treatment

Male and female outbred rats aged 3 months were used as the experimental test system. Lithium ascorbate was administered once daily by intragastric gavage for 180 consecutive days. The chronic toxicity study included three lithium ascorbate dose levels: 10 mg/kg, 100 mg/kg, and 500 mg/kg. A control substance was administered to control animals using the same route.

Clinical, physiological, hematological, and biochemical assessment

During the treatment period, animals were monitored for survival, clinical signs of intoxication, general appearance, behavior, body-weight dynamics, water intake, and food intake. Physiological parameters were also evaluated, including open-field behavioral testing, blood pressure, and electrocardiographic parameters. Hematological and serum biochemical parameters were assessed to evaluate systemic effects of repeated lithium ascorbate administration.

Pathology, reproductive assessment, mutagenicity, immunotoxicity, and local tolerance

At the end of the study, animals underwent macroscopic and microscopic examination of internal organs. Organ mass coefficients were calculated and compared across groups. Reproductive safety was assessed by morphometric and histological examination of reproductive organs in males and females. The study also included assessment of local irritant action, elements of mutagenic action, and immunotoxicity.

Statistical analysis

Parametric one-way ANOVA was used for body-weight and body-weight-gain analyses, and Tukey's HSD test was used for selected organ-mass-coefficient comparisons. Statistical significance was interpreted in relation to control values and evaluated together with the consistency, dose relationship, sex specificity, and biological relevance of the findings.

Results

Survival and clinical observations

Lithium ascorbate administered at 10 mg/kg did not affect the appearance or general condition of male or female rats. Animals in this dose group did not differ from controls in appearance or behavior, no sex-related differences were recorded, and no clinical signs of intoxication were observed throughout the experiment. In males treated with 100 mg/kg, and in most females receiving the same dose, no abnormalities in the clinical picture were reported.

At 500 mg/kg, polyuria was observed in both male and female rats during daily clinical examination and persisted for approximately 3–4 weeks. In males receiving 500 mg/kg, decreased motor activity, reduced muscle mass, and decreased turgor were noted approximately one week after treatment initiation; these findings persisted for approximately two weeks. From

one month after treatment initiation until the end of the study, no further abnormalities in the clinical picture were recorded in male rats at 500 mg/kg. Deaths were reported in female rats in the 100 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg dose groups.

Food intake, water intake, and body weight

Water and food intake in rats of both sexes receiving 10 mg/kg or 100 mg/kg lithium ascorbate did not differ from control values. At 500 mg/kg, polydipsia was observed in both sexes, resulting in increased water intake compared with controls; however, food intake in this dose group did not differ from the control group.

Statistically significant differences in body weight and absolute body-weight gain were reported in male and female rats receiving 100 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg compared with controls two weeks after the start of the study. In males, one-way ANOVA also identified statistically significant differences in body weight and absolute body-weight gain at weeks 17, 18, and 19, with mean values approximately 10–20% lower than in the control group. No other statistically significant body-weight differences were reported. Overall, body weight tended to increase throughout the study in both control and treated animals.

Behavioral, cardiovascular, and electrocardiographic findings

Open-field test scores did not differ significantly between treated and control rats of either sex. Blood pressure values also showed no statistically significant differences between control animals and rats receiving lithium ascorbate at any tested dose. After 180 days of administration, no statistically significant differences in electrocardiographic parameters were recorded in male or female rats treated with lithium ascorbate compared with controls. One month after the end of administration, male rats receiving 10 mg/kg showed a statistically significant increase in P-wave level compared with controls, with an average increase of approximately 33%.

Hematology and serum biochemistry

In female rats, the report describes sporadic statistically significant changes in hematological parameters after lithium ascorbate administration compared with controls. In male rats, 180 days of treatment with lithium ascorbate at 10 mg/kg, 100 mg/kg, and 500 mg/kg was associated with statistically significant decreases in red blood cell count, hemoglobin concentration, and hematocrit. One month after the end of treatment, males receiving 100 mg/kg showed statistically significant increases in hemoglobin and hematocrit; these values remained within reference ranges. Significant changes in serum biochemical parameters were also reported in animals receiving lithium ascorbate.

Mutagenicity, immunotoxicity, reproductive organs, and local tolerance

No immunotoxic or mutagenic effects were reported following repeated lithium ascorbate administration. Morphometric and histological examination of male and female reproductive organs showed no statistically significant differences between treated groups and controls. No local irritant action was reported.

Organ weights and pathology

Organ mass coefficients in female rats treated with lithium ascorbate did not differ significantly from control values. In males, Tukey's HSD analysis identified statistically significant differences in liver and kidney mass coefficients one month after the end of administration. However, these changes were not consistent across groups and were interpreted as individual rather than generalized findings. No other statistically significant organ mass coefficient differences were recorded. Macroscopic and microscopic examinations did not reveal pronounced pathomorphological changes attributable to lithium ascorbate, indicating good tolerability under the conditions of the study.

Study 2: Allergenic properties

Materials and Methods

Study design and regulatory compliance

A preclinical study was conducted to evaluate the allergenic properties of lithium ascorbate substance manufactured by Normopharm LLC, Russia. The study was performed at JSC "NPO HOUSE OF PHARMACY," Leningrad Region, Russia, under study code 1.21/21. The final report was dated September 13, 2021. The study was conducted in accordance with OECD Good Laboratory Practice principles, except that identification, purity, and stability testing of the test substance were not performed by the research institution; these parameters were determined by the sponsor according to standard methods. The study was reviewed and approved by the institutional Bioethics Commission and was conducted in accordance with the principles of ethical animal handling, including the Three Rs and Directive 2010/63/EU.

The objective of the study was to assess whether lithium ascorbate could induce immediate-type or delayed-type allergic reactions. Immediate-type hypersensitivity was evaluated using the active cutaneous anaphylaxis test in guinea pigs. Delayed-type hypersensitivity was evaluated using a delayed-type hypersensitivity reaction test in outbred mice.

Test and control substances

The test object was a lithium ascorbate substance, coded T-1.21/21, manufactured by Normopharm LLC, Russia. The control substance and vehicle was 0.9% sodium chloride saline

solution, coded M-1.21/21 and manufactured by Gematek LLC, Russia. Freund's complete adjuvant was used as a sensitization agent in the delayed-type hypersensitivity test.

Animals and housing

The study used male white guinea pigs and male outbred mice obtained from the kennel of JSC "NPO HOUSE OF PHARMACY." The total number of animals was 46 guinea pigs and 52 mice, including animals used for determination of the challenge dose. Guinea pigs were sexually mature and up to 12 weeks of age at the start of test substance administration, with initial body weights of 498–718 g. Mice were sexually mature and up to 8 weeks of age, with initial body weights of 28.92–39.15 g.

Animals were allocated to groups using modified block randomization to reduce allocation bias. Before the start of experimental procedures, animals were adapted for 5 days and monitored daily for clinical conditions. Animals were housed under standard laboratory conditions with controlled temperature, humidity, air exchange, and a 12-hour light/dark cycle. Feed and water were provided ad libitum. Guinea pigs additionally received ascorbic acid supplementation in drinking water.

Active cutaneous anaphylaxis test in guinea pigs

The active cutaneous anaphylaxis test was used to evaluate immediate-type hypersensitivity. Guinea pigs were divided into four main groups of 10 males each. Groups 1–3 received lithium ascorbate at doses of 46.3, 232, and 463 mg/kg, respectively, corresponding to the human therapeutic dose, fivefold human therapeutic dose, and tenfold human therapeutic dose after interspecies dose conversion. Group 4 received the control substance.

During the sensitization phase, guinea pigs received the test or control substance subcutaneously into the withers area on day 1 and intramuscularly into the thigh area on days 3 and 5. Animals were then clinically observed through the challenge phase.

Before the challenge stage, the challenge concentration was determined in six intact male guinea pigs. Lithium ascorbate was administered intradermally at concentrations of 10, 1, and 0.1 mg/mL in a volume of 50 μ L/animal. Saline was administered intradermally at a separate skin site as a reactivity control. Since none of the tested concentrations caused local skin irritation after 24 hours, 10 mg/mL was selected as the challenge concentration.

On day 18, sensitized guinea pigs received a single intradermal challenge injection of lithium ascorbate at 10 mg/mL in a volume of 50 μ L/animal into the shaved skin of the back. Saline was injected intradermally at a separate site as a control. Twenty minutes after challenge administration, animals received 0.5 mL of 1% Evans blue dye intravenously. Thirty minutes

after dye administration, animals were euthanized, and the skin at the injection site was excised. The presence and size of blue staining at the injection site were used to assess the reaction.

Delayed-type hypersensitivity test in mice

The delayed-type hypersensitivity test was used to assess delayed allergic reactions. Mice were divided into four main groups of 10 males each. Groups 8–10 received lithium ascorbate at doses of 61.7, 123.3, and 250 mg/kg, respectively, corresponding to one-half of the human therapeutic dose, the human therapeutic dose, and twice the human therapeutic dose after interspecies dose conversion and adjustment for solubility constraints. Group 4 received the control substance.

During the sensitization phase, the test or control substance was administered once intradermally at the base of the tail in Freund's complete adjuvant, at a dosing volume of 60 μ L/animal. Animals were observed daily after sensitization.

The challenge concentration was selected using 12 intact male mice. Lithium ascorbate was administered under the plantar aponeurosis of the right pelvic extremity at concentrations of 10, 1, and 0.1 mg/mL in a volume of 40 μ L/animal. Saline was administered under the plantar aponeurosis of the left pelvic extremity as a control. Because none of the tested concentrations caused tissue irritation or edema after 24 hours, 10 mg/mL was selected as the challenge concentration.

On day 6, sensitized mice received a single challenge injection of lithium ascorbate at 10 mg/mL under the plantar aponeurosis of the right pelvic extremity in a volume of 40 μ L/animal. Saline was injected into the left pelvic extremity as the paired control. Twenty-four hours later, mice were euthanized using CO₂ followed by cervical dislocation. The pelvic extremities were excised at the tarsotibial joint and weighed. The delayed-type hypersensitivity response index was calculated using the weight of the test extremity and the control extremity.

Clinical observations and body weight

General clinical observations were performed daily. Animals were examined in the cage, in the hands, and in an open area. Recorded parameters included behavior, coordination, response to stimuli, muscle tone, skin condition, eyes and conjunctiva, nasal mucosa, oral cavity, injection-site reactions, and mortality. Body weight was recorded before the first administration of the study objects. In guinea pigs, body weight was used to determine administration volume. In mice, body weight was used to ensure that group means did not differ by more than 20%.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics were calculated for all data. The Shapiro–Wilk test was used to assess normality. Normally distributed data were summarized as mean and standard error of the mean.

Non-normally distributed data were summarized as median and interquartile range. For normally distributed data, one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test was used. For non-normally distributed data and percentage data, the Kruskal–Wallis test was used. Pairwise comparisons were performed using the Mann–Whitney test where applicable. Statistical significance was defined as $p < 0.05$. Analyses were performed using Statistica 10.0.

Results

Challenge-dose selection in guinea pigs

In intact guinea pigs, intradermal administration of lithium ascorbate at concentrations of 10, 1, and 0.1 mg/mL did not cause local skin irritation 24 hours after administration. Therefore, 10 mg/mL was selected as the maximum non-irritant concentration for the challenge stage of the active cutaneous anaphylaxis test.

Active cutaneous anaphylaxis test

No immediate-type hypersensitivity reactions were observed in guinea pigs sensitized with lithium ascorbate at 46.3, 232, or 463 mg/kg. After intradermal challenge with lithium ascorbate at 10 mg/mL and subsequent intravenous administration of Evans blue dye, no blue staining was detected at the injection sites. The reaction was therefore recorded as zero in all groups, and no statistical analysis was performed. These findings indicate that lithium ascorbate did not induce active cutaneous anaphylaxis in guinea pigs under the conditions of the study.

Challenge-dose selection in mice

In intact mice, administration of lithium ascorbate at concentrations of 10, 1, and 0.1 mg/mL under the plantar aponeurosis did not produce tissue irritation or edema of the experimental extremity 24 hours after administration. Analysis of the response index showed no statistically significant differences between groups by the Kruskal–Wallis test ($p > 0.05$). Accordingly, 10 mg/mL was selected as the challenge concentration for the delayed-type hypersensitivity test.

Delayed-type hypersensitivity test

In the delayed-type hypersensitivity test, no clinically meaningful delayed allergic reaction was observed in mice sensitized with lithium ascorbate at 61.7, 123.3, or 250 mg/kg. The Kruskal–Wallis test did not identify a statistically significant group effect, although the result approached statistical significance ($p = 0.055$). Subsequent pairwise analysis using the Mann–Whitney test showed a statistically significant increase in the response index in mice treated with 123.3 mg/kg compared with mice treated with 250 mg/kg and with controls ($p < 0.05$). However, no statistically significant difference was observed between the highest dose group, 250 mg/kg, and the control group. The report therefore interpreted the isolated

response-index difference as clinically insignificant. Overall, no delayed-type hypersensitivity reaction was detected following lithium ascorbate sensitization and challenge.

Body weight

Body weights of guinea pigs and mice were recorded before the first administration of the study substances. Baseline body-weight data were normally distributed. No statistically significant differences in initial body weight were found between corresponding experimental and control groups ($p > 0.05$).

Clinical observations

Daily clinical examination of guinea pigs and mice revealed no deaths and no abnormalities in clinical condition, appearance, or behavior during the experimental period. No deviations were observed in cage behavior, open-field behavior, response to stimuli, muscle tone, skin condition, mucous membranes, or injection sites when lithium ascorbate-treated animals were compared with control animals.

Overall allergenicity assessment

Under the experimental conditions used in this study, lithium ascorbate did not induce immediate-type hypersensitivity in guinea pigs or delayed-type hypersensitivity in mice within the tested dose ranges. The study report concluded that lithium ascorbate did not demonstrate sensitizing or antigenic properties in the applied test systems.

Study 3: Pharmacological safety

Study design and regulatory compliance

A preclinical pharmacological safety study was conducted to evaluate the effects of lithium ascorbate substance following a single intragastric administration in rats. The study was performed at CJSC “Saint Petersburg Institute of Pharmacy,” Leningrad Region, Russia, under Good Laboratory Practice principles. The study report states that GLP compliance was maintained, except that identity, purity, and stability testing of the test substance was not performed by the research institution. These parameters were determined by the sponsor using standard methods. The study was reviewed and approved by the institutional Bioethics Commission and was conducted in accordance with ethical principles for animal research, including the Three Rs and Directive 2010/63/EU.

The objective of the study was to assess the pharmacological safety of lithium ascorbate after a single intragastric dose, with specific evaluation of the respiratory, cardiovascular, and central nervous systems. The experimental part of the study was conducted in July–August 2021.

Test and control substances

The test object was a lithium ascorbate substance manufactured by Normopharm LLC, Russia. The report identifies the test substance as a substance form of lithium ascorbate, stored protected from light at +2°C to +8°C, with short-term storage at room temperature permitted for 3–5 days. The control substance was 0.9% sodium chloride solution manufactured by Gematek LLC, Russia.

Animals and housing

The study used 40 male Wistar rats obtained from JSC “NPO HOUSE OF PHARMACY.” Animals were up to 12 weeks old at group formation, with a reported mean baseline body weight of 227.5 ± 1.55 g. Rats were clinically healthy at transfer to the study and were adapted for 5–7 days before dosing. During the adaptation period, animals were examined daily, and no abnormalities in clinical condition were observed.

Animals were assigned to groups using modified block randomization to reduce investigator-related allocation bias. Rats were housed under standard laboratory conditions in groups of five, with a 12-hour light/dark cycle, controlled temperature and humidity, and approximately 10–15 room air exchanges per hour. Feed was provided according to institutional feeding regimens, except for planned feed deprivation before dosing. Water was provided ad libitum throughout the experiment.

Dose selection and administration

Lithium ascorbate and the control substance were administered once by intragastric gavage, as this route was considered an analogue of the intended oral route in clinical use. Animals were observed for 14 days after administration and euthanized on day 15. Rats were deprived of food for 16 hours before dosing, while water remained available ad libitum.

The study included four groups of 10 males each. Group 1 received the control substance at 0 mg/kg. Groups 2–3 received lithium ascorbate at 10 mg/kg, 50 mg/kg, and 150 mg/kg, respectively. These doses were described in the report as the highest therapeutic dose, fivefold highest therapeutic dose, and fifteenfold highest therapeutic dose. The dosing volume was 1 mL/kg for all groups, with lithium ascorbate administered as a suspension at concentrations of 10, 50, or 150 mg/mL.

Clinical observations, body weight, and body temperature

Animals were continuously observed for 30 minutes after administration and then monitored daily until day 14. Clinical examinations were performed before dosing, 30 minutes after dosing, on day 2, and then weekly. Examinations included assessment in the cage, in the hands, and in an

open area. Recorded parameters included behavior, response to stimuli, skin and mucous membrane appearance, discharge, muscle tone, motor coordination, respiratory signs, urination and defecation, and mortality.

Body weight was recorded one day before administration and then weekly. Body temperature was measured rectally before administration, 30 minutes after administration, on day 2, and then weekly using an IM-10 patient monitor.

Respiratory safety assessment

Respiratory safety was assessed 24 hours after administration by measuring respiratory rate in anesthetized animals. Respiratory rate was recorded using a pneumograph with a piezo sensor before electrocardiographic recording.

Cardiovascular safety assessment

Cardiovascular safety was assessed on day 2 of the experiment by electrocardiography and systolic blood pressure measurement. For ECG recording, animals were anesthetized with Zoletil 100 and Xila and fixed on an operating table. ECGs were recorded using a veterinary computer electrocardiograph. The evaluated ECG parameters included heart rate, RR interval, P-wave duration, PQ interval, QRS duration, and QT interval. Systolic blood pressure was measured non-invasively in anesthetized animals after ECG recording.

Central nervous system safety assessment

Central nervous system safety was evaluated 24 hours after administration using the Irwin functional observational battery and the Open Field test. The Irwin battery included assessment of behavior, neurological signs, autonomic signs, motor coordination, muscle tone, reflex responses, sensory responses, abnormal movements, tremors, convulsions, salivation, lacrimation, piloerection, ptosis, startle response, and other functional parameters. The Open Field test was used to evaluate individual behavior, orientation, and exploratory activity. Recorded parameters included horizontal activity, vertical activity, center visits, urination, defecation, and autogrooming.

Euthanasia

Animals were euthanized on day 15 using carbon dioxide followed by severing of the major blood vessels. This method was selected in accordance with Directive 2010/63/EU and was performed by competent personnel to minimize pain, suffering, and distress.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics were applied to all data. The Shapiro–Wilk test was used to assess normality. Normally distributed data were summarized as mean and standard error of the mean, whereas non-normally distributed data were summarized as median and interquartile range. For normally distributed data, one-way ANOVA was used, followed by Tukey’s post hoc test when a significant factor effect was detected. Student’s t-test was used for two-group comparisons where appropriate. For non-normally distributed data, the Kruskal–Wallis test was used, followed by nonparametric average-rank multiple comparisons if a significant factor effect was detected. The Mann–Whitney U-test was used for two-group comparisons. Statistical significance was defined as $p < 0.05$. Analyses were performed using Statistica 10.

Results

Survival and clinical observations

No deaths were recorded during the experiment. Clinical observations and scheduled clinical examinations did not reveal abnormalities in the appearance, general condition, or behavior of animals in any lithium ascorbate-treated group compared with controls. The response to stimuli and handling was standard and moderately pronounced in all animals. Body condition was satisfactory, the hair coat was smooth and shiny, and no alopecia was reported. Muscle tone was moderate, and no gait abnormalities or motor coordination disorders were observed.

Skin turgor and integrity were preserved, and no palpable masses were noted. Visible mucous membranes were pale pink, shiny, and intact. No exophthalmos, ocular swelling, conjunctival hyperemia, lacrimation, nasal discharge, salivation disorders, abnormal urination, abnormal defecation, or unusual behavior was reported. Respiration was normal in all experimental animals. Overall, the clinical condition of rats receiving lithium ascorbate did not differ from that of control animals.

Body weight

Baseline body weight did not differ significantly between groups and did not deviate from the group mean by more than 20%. Repeated-measures analysis identified a statistically significant effect of repeated measurement, consistent with physiological weight gain over the study period, while the group factor was not significant. Intergroup comparison using Tukey’s test showed no statistically significant differences between lithium ascorbate-treated groups and the control group. Therefore, a single intragastric administration of lithium ascorbate at 10, 50, or 150 mg/kg did not affect body-weight dynamics in male rats.

Body temperature

Baseline body temperature did not differ significantly between groups. Repeated-measures analysis did not show statistically significant effects of either time or group. No statistically

significant differences in body temperature were found between lithium ascorbate-treated animals and controls. Thus, a single intragastric administration of lithium ascorbate did not affect body temperature in male rats.

Respiratory safety

Respiratory rate was measured on day 2, 24 hours after administration. The data were normally distributed, and one-way ANOVA did not show a significant group effect on respiratory rate. No statistically significant differences were found between lithium ascorbate-treated animals and controls. Therefore, lithium ascorbate did not produce detectable effects on respiratory function under the conditions of the study.

Cardiovascular safety

ECG parameters measured on day 2 were normally distributed, and one-way ANOVA did not identify statistically significant differences between groups for the evaluated ECG variables. Systolic blood pressure data were also normally distributed, and one-way ANOVA did not show a significant group effect.

Although not statistically significant, the report noted slight increases in heart rate and systolic blood pressure in the highest-dose group receiving 150 mg/kg. These increases did not exceed 7% relative to control values and were not considered clinically significant. Overall, the absence of statistically significant changes in ECG or systolic blood pressure parameters indicated that lithium ascorbate did not exert a significant effect on cardiovascular function following single intragastric administration.

Central nervous system safety

In the Irwin functional observational battery, minor deviations from normal values were observed for the parameter “movement along the corridor” in both lithium ascorbate-treated groups and the control group. These deviations were not dose-dependent and were multidirectional within groups. The report interpreted these findings as individual animal characteristics rather than treatment-related effects. No clinically significant effects of lithium ascorbate on central nervous system function were identified.

In the Open Field test, normally distributed parameters, including the number of wall rears and the number of squares visited, showed no significant group effect by one-way ANOVA. Non-normally distributed parameters, including center visits, free rears, autogrooming, urination, and defecation, showed no statistically significant differences by the Kruskal–Wallis test. These results indicate that lithium ascorbate did not significantly alter locomotor, exploratory, emotional, or grooming-related behavior 24 hours after administration.

Overall pharmacological safety assessment

A single intragastric administration of lithium ascorbate at 10, 50, or 150 mg/kg did not cause mortality, clinical signs of intoxication, abnormal body-weight dynamics, changes in body temperature, or clinically significant effects on the respiratory, cardiovascular, or central nervous systems in male Wistar rats. Under the conditions of the study, lithium ascorbate showed no detectable adverse pharmacological safety signal in the evaluated functional systems.

Discussion

The present studies provide an integrated preclinical assessment of the pharmacological safety, repeated-dose toxicity, allergenic potential, and selected toxicological properties of lithium ascorbate. Across the evaluated experimental systems, lithium ascorbate did not produce detectable adverse effects on the central nervous, cardiovascular, or respiratory systems following a single intragastric administration of up to 150 mg/kg in male rats. Repeated administration for 180 days was not associated with overt clinical signs of intoxication at the lowest tested dose of 10 mg/kg, and no treatment-related mutagenic, immunotoxic, local irritant, or histopathological effects were reported. Lithium ascorbate also did not induce immediate-type hypersensitivity in guinea pigs or a consistent delayed-type hypersensitivity response in mice. Collectively, these findings support a preliminary safety profile for lithium ascorbate under the specific conditions of the studies. However, the adverse findings observed during repeated exposure at higher doses, together with several methodological limitations, require careful consideration before conclusions can be extended to clinical use.

The single-dose pharmacological safety study evaluated the central nervous, cardiovascular, and respiratory systems, which represent the principal organ systems examined within a core safety pharmacology battery. The absence of mortality, abnormal clinical signs, changes in body temperature, altered locomotor or exploratory behavior, or statistically significant effects on respiratory rate, electrocardiographic variables, and systolic blood pressure indicates that lithium ascorbate did not produce an acute adverse pharmacodynamic signal at doses of 10–150 mg/kg. The small increases in heart rate and systolic blood pressure observed at 150 mg/kg were limited in magnitude, did not reach statistical significance, and were not accompanied by changes in other cardiovascular parameters. These observations suggest that the findings were unlikely to represent a biologically meaningful acute cardiovascular effect. Nevertheless, the study assessed a single administration, used only male animals, and evaluated several functional endpoints at one principal post-dose time point. The results therefore do not exclude transient effects occurring before or after the selected assessment period, sex-specific responses, or cardiovascular effects that may emerge during repeated exposure.

The repeated-dose study provides a more differentiated safety profile. Lithium ascorbate administered at 10 mg/kg for 180 days did not affect the general appearance, behavior, food

intake, or water intake of male or female rats. At 100 mg/kg, most animals also showed no overt clinical abnormalities, although statistically significant changes in body weight and body-weight gain were observed early in the treatment period. In contrast, administration of 500 mg/kg was associated with polyuria and polydipsia in both sexes, as well as transient reductions in motor activity, muscle mass, and skin turgor in males. These findings indicate that the highest dose exceeded the level at which lithium ascorbate was well tolerated during prolonged administration.

The occurrence of polyuria and polydipsia is particularly relevant because impaired urinary concentrating ability is a recognized class-related effect of lithium salts (McKnight et al., 2012; Gitlin, 2016).

Deaths were reported in female rats receiving 100 and 500 mg/kg lithium ascorbate. Because the causes of death, temporal relationship to treatment, associated clinical findings, and pathological correlates are not described in the available results, these events cannot be considered unrelated to treatment. The occurrence of mortality in females, but not in males, also raises the possibility of sex-dependent differences in susceptibility, systemic exposure, or lithium disposition. This observation is important because the single-dose pharmacological safety and allergenicity studies were conducted exclusively in male animals. A more complete assessment should therefore include detailed evaluation of the female deaths and balanced inclusion of both sexes in subsequent studies.

Several hematological and biochemical changes were reported following repeated lithium ascorbate administration. In males, decreases in red blood cell count, hemoglobin concentration, and hematocrit occurred at all tested doses after 180 days of treatment. The toxicological significance of these findings depends on their magnitude, relationship to dose, position relative to historical control and reference ranges, association with reticulocyte counts or other hematological indices, and reversibility after treatment cessation. Similarly, the reported serum biochemical changes cannot be fully interpreted without information on their direction, effect size, dose dependence, and relationship to organ pathology. The isolated changes in liver and kidney mass coefficients and the increase in P-wave level observed during the recovery period were not supported by a consistent dose–response relationship or corresponding histopathological findings. These results may represent biological variation, but they warrant cautious interpretation rather than dismissal solely on the basis of statistical inconsistency.

The absence of pronounced macroscopic or microscopic lesions is an important finding, particularly after 180 days of exposure. However, histopathological normality should be interpreted together with functional, clinical pathology, and survival data. The combination of female deaths, high-dose polyuria and polydipsia, transient reductions in body-weight gain, and hematological changes indicates that repeated-dose toxicity was not entirely absent. Accordingly, the available reporting does not permit a robust assignment of a no-observed-adverse-effect

level. The lowest tested dose of 10 mg/kg was not associated with overt clinical toxicity, but the hematological findings at this dose require further evaluation before it can be classified as non-adverse.

The negative findings for mutagenicity-related endpoints, immunotoxicity, local irritation, and reproductive-organ morphology provide additional evidence that lithium ascorbate did not produce broad toxicological effects in the applied test systems. Nevertheless, these results should be described according to their experimental scope. Assessment of reproductive-organ weights and histology does not substitute for studies of fertility, mating performance, embryofetal development, or pre- and postnatal development. Similarly, the absence of effects in selected mutagenicity and immunotoxicity assays does not establish the absence of genotoxic or immunological risk across a complete regulatory testing battery. Further studies using a defined set of in vitro and in vivo genotoxicity assays and guideline-based reproductive and developmental toxicity designs would strengthen the safety characterization.

The allergenicity studies did not identify immediate-type hypersensitivity in guinea pigs or a consistent delayed-type hypersensitivity response in mice. In the delayed-type hypersensitivity study, the overall group comparison did not reach statistical significance, and the isolated increase in the response index at the intermediate dose was not reproduced at the highest dose. The absence of a monotonic dose–response relationship and the lack of clinical evidence of local inflammation argue against a treatment-related sensitization effect. However, negative findings in these animal models cannot exclude rare hypersensitivity reactions in humans or reactions arising through mechanisms not represented by the selected assays.

An important limitation of the current study program is the absence of toxicokinetic data. Doses were expressed as the mass of lithium ascorbate rather than as elemental lithium exposure, and plasma or tissue lithium concentrations were not reported. This prevents direct comparison with conventional lithium salts and limits interpretation of the exposure margins achieved in the animal studies. A head-to-head comparison with lithium carbonate or another clinically established lithium salt, normalized to elemental lithium dose and supported by pharmacokinetic measurements, would be required to determine whether lithium ascorbate has a genuinely improved safety profile. The present findings should therefore not be interpreted as evidence that lithium ascorbate is safer than conventional lithium preparations.

Future studies should focus on clarifying the repeated-dose findings and defining exposure-based safety margins. These investigations should include detailed toxicokinetic analysis, elemental lithium-equivalent dosing, quantitative assessment of renal concentrating function, serum electrolyte measurements, comprehensive hematological evaluation, and determination of the causes of death observed in female rats. Additional cardiovascular studies should assess the potential for effects on ventricular repolarization and cardiac conduction over an appropriate range of exposures. Broader genotoxicity, reproductive and developmental toxicity, and, where

required, non-rodent repeated-dose studies would be necessary to support a more complete nonclinical safety assessment.

In conclusion, lithium ascorbate showed no detectable acute adverse pharmacological effects on the central nervous, cardiovascular, or respiratory systems and did not demonstrate sensitizing, mutagenic, immunotoxic, local irritant, or reproductive-organ effects in the applied experimental models. Repeated administration at the lowest tested dose was not associated with overt clinical toxicity, whereas higher doses produced findings consistent with reduced tolerability, including polyuria, polydipsia, altered body-weight dynamics, and mortality in female rats. These results support continued investigation of lithium ascorbate but do not, in their current form, establish clinical safety or superiority over conventional lithium salts.

Data availability

All source data for this study are available upon reasonable request.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, Rastashanskiy V.V.; methodology, software, validation, formal analysis, data collection and investigation, resources, data curation, writing - original draft preparation Anisimova M.A. , Belyaeva M.M., Vataeva A.A., Zarenkov E.V., Kashina T.V., Kozlov A.A., Shultz A.V., Roshchina E.A., Aleshanova N.A., Vasiliev A.V., Vavilova V. A., Gushchin Y.A.; writing- review and editing Gromova O.A.; supervision, project administration, Gromova O.A., Rastashanskiy V.V. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding

The studies were funded by Normopharm LLC, Russia.

Ethics declarations

This research was conducted according to the GLP/OECD guidelines (OECD, 1998a). These studies were reviewed at the meetings of the Bioethics Commission for compliance with the “Three R’s” principles and Directive 2010/63/EU.

Competing interests

The experiments were paid for by Normopharm LLC, Russia.

Abbreviations

ECG — electrocardiogram

HSD — honestly significant difference; used in Tukey's HSD post hoc test

LLC — Limited Liability Company

OECD GLP — Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development Good Laboratory Practice

PQ — PQ interval; the ECG interval from the beginning of the P wave to the beginning of the QRS complex

QRS — QRS complex; the ECG waveform representing ventricular depolarization

QT interval — the ECG interval from the beginning of the QRS complex to the end of the T wave

RR — respiratory rate

$\mu\text{L}/\text{animal}$ — microliters per animal; dosing volume administered to each animal

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